

DURABILITY OF POSTBUCKLING FIBRE COMPOSITE SHEAR PANELS

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SUMMARY: An experimental investigation to characterise the performance of thin, stiffened, composite panels in the postbuckled state has been undertaken. Static and fatigue shear testing was performed on three-blade-stiffened panels with skin thickness of 1 mm and a working section of 250 x 250 mm. Panels with an artificial delamination and others which had been impact damaged were also tested. As well as laboratory testing, a series of environmental exposure tests was conducted under tropical conditions. Initial results indicate that undamaged panels are capable of withstanding cycling at two thirds of the static ultimate load. Panels containing large artificial delaminations suffered considerable delamination growth which stabilised after less than 100,000 cycles. These panels were still capable of carrying significant load, demonstrating their inherent damage tolerance.

KEYWORDS: postbuckling, durability, environmental effects, fatigue, stiffened structures

INTRODUCTION

The progressive introduction of advanced fibre composite materials into primary aerospace structures has enabled significant performance improvements to be achieved. However, the use of composites in stiffened panels has generally been restricted to designs which do not buckle under compression and shear loads for various reasons including some relating to uncertainties associated with their long term durability. In order to improve the relative competitiveness of composites in primary structural applications, this conservative philosophy needs to be reconsidered and postbuckling structures used. Prior to the introduction of designs intended to operate at high buckling ratios, a thorough understanding of both the static and fatigue characteristics of postbuckling composite panels is necessary.

The postbuckling performance of metal panels has been investigated extensively and is relatively well understood. One of the main concerns with metal postbuckling structures is the permanent deformation resulting from the large deflections. Similar stress relief due to yielding is not available in practical composite lay-ups which could result in sudden failure. Due to the poor through-thickness properties of laminated composites, likely failure modes include delamination and stiffener-skin separation. Another area of concern for composite structures is degradation from exposure to moisture, elevated temperature and ultraviolet (UV) radiation. The performance of the panels over long periods of time must also be

evaluated. Much of the work conducted in this area to date has not adequately addressed these aspects.

Experimental and analytical investigations into the buckling and postbuckling response of composite shear panels have been undertaken by a small number of researchers. Some significant work has been performed by Weller and Singer [1] who investigated the buckling and postbuckling response of unstiffened shear webs and “T” and “J” stiffened panels. An aspect of the work involved cycling the shear webs at various load levels for up to 250,000 cycles. It was concluded that such panels could withstand fatigue loading, with reductions in residual strength of up to 20%. The performance of flat, postbuckling, “T” and hat-stiffened composite shear webs was investigated by Agarwal [2]. It was found that these panels could withstand 500,000 cycles with little loss in strength despite delamination and stiffener-skin separation. Panhwar et al [3] investigated the fatigue performance of flat, unstiffened panels under shear. These panels were cycled for up to 3 million cycles and it was concluded that they could operate safely at up to seven times the buckling load.

Environmental and fatigue testing of composite materials are usually conducted in the laboratory under accelerated conditions. To investigate the validity of this testing methodology, an extensive study was carried out by Hoffman and Bielawski [4] into the long term environmental exposure effects on composite materials. Studies were carried out on both laboratory and field specimens over a period of 10 years. It was concluded that the field exposure specimens were necessary, as some important long term behaviour patterns were not predicted by the laboratory testing.

In view of this, the present program of research involves theoretical and experimental investigations of the postbuckling characteristics of thin, stiffened, composite shear panels. Experiments were undertaken using integral-blade-stiffened panels with a skin thickness of 1 mm, tested in shear. Emphasis was placed on assessing the effect of a high number of cycles coupled with long term exposure to adverse environments. Static and fatigue failure modes are being determined and methods to predict the buckling load, postbuckling behaviour and strength have been developed using finite element techniques [5].

APPROACH

Test Specimens

Tests were performed on three-blade-stiffened panels, as shown in Fig. 1. The overall dimensions of the panels were 340 x 340 mm with working dimensions of 250 x 250 mm. The integral blade-stiffeners were 25 mm high with run-out angles of 45°. The skins and stiffeners were co-cured in an autoclave using flexible tooling. The material used to manufacture the panels was T300/914C carbon fibre/epoxy, unidirectional, pre-impregnated, zero-bleed tape. The skins of the panels were 1 mm thick consisting of eight plies of tape and the stiffeners were 2 mm thick consisting of 16 plies. The clamping regions of the panels were built-up to a thickness of 1.5 mm consisting of 12 plies. The stacking sequences of the panels are detailed in Fig. 1. A design criterion was for the stacking sequence of the stiffeners to be symmetrical. As shown in Fig. 2, the top four plies of the skin formed part of the stiffener to improve the interface strength, resulting in the lay-up of alternate bays of the skin not being symmetric. The panels were trimmed and drilled to the geometry shown in Fig. 1 and inspected using through-transmission, ultrasonic C-Scan to detect manufacturing flaws.

To assess the effect of damage, a number of panels were manufactured with a 50 mm diameter piece of teflon film imbedded in the lay-up in the centre of the panel. The location of the film in the stacking sequence is shown in Fig. 3. This situation is representative of a delamination introduced during manufacture or resulting from in-service damage. The presence of the insert was verified by C-Scan of the panel. Other panels were subjected to low speed impact using a 25 mm diameter impactor to produce barely visible impact damage. An incident energy of 3.4 J was used of which approximately 1.0 J was absorbed. The impact location coincided with a buckle peak and the damage area was assessed by C-Scan.

Fig. 1: Three-blade-stiffened panel dimensions.

Fig. 2: Detail of the integral stiffener lay-up.

Fig. 3: Location of the teflon insert under the centre stiffener.

Test Procedure

Static Testing

Panels were tested in a “picture frame” shear fixture with anti-slip strips placed between the panel and the rig edge members to achieve effective load transfer through frictional contact. A number of panels were fitted with three-element strain gauge rosettes, located front and back at various locations on the panel. A linear variable differential transformer (LVDT) was employed to measure the out-of-plane displacement of a buckle peak during the tests. The shadow moiré interferometry technique was also used to qualitatively correlate the buckle shapes and out-of-plane displacements with those obtained through analytical techniques [5].

A uniaxial tensile load was applied diagonally through the top and bottom pins using a servo-hydraulic universal testing machine in displacement control mode. The load was applied in the direction of the -45° fibres of the panels; this represents the applied load and has been converted to shear flow throughout this paper. A data acquisition system was used to record the load, stroke, strains and out-of-plane displacement continuously during testing. When using moiré interferometry, the tests were paused at various load levels to photograph the buckled patterns.

Fatigue Testing

Laboratory fatigue testing has been carried out on a number of panels using the “picture frame” shear fixture. Tests have been conducted at stress ratio (R) values of 0.4 and -1.0 with maximum shear buckling ratios of 2.0. The R value of 0.4 was chosen to simulate the cycling of a wing skin from just below buckling load to limit load. The R value of -1.0 represents the fully reversed fatigue loading experienced by aircraft components such as fins or rudders. For all laboratory fatigue tests, loads were applied using a servo-hydraulic universal testing machine in load control mode. Cyclic frequencies between 2 and 4 Hz have been used for the testing.

Environmental Testing

Long term environmental testing was performed at the Australian Defence Science and Technology Organisation (DSTO) tropical test facility located near Innisfail in Northern Queensland. The site is at a latitude of 17° South where the annual rainfall is 3,500 mm and the average daily humidity is 80%. There are 2,300 hours of sunlight experienced per year with an average daily maximum temperature of 28°C . Surface temperatures of up to 84°C have been recorded. Previous tests on carbon fibre/epoxy specimens carried out at the facility by Chalkley and Chester [6] concluded that a moisture content of 0.7% was reached. The specimens were also subjected to hygrothermal cycling as the temperature varied throughout the day.

“Hot/wet” conditions are critical for structures manufactured from carbon fibre/epoxy composites. Reductions in the strength of composites occur when operating temperatures approach the glass transition temperature, T_g . This is the temperature at which the epoxy matrix changes from a glass like state to a rubbery state which is associated with a drastic reduction of properties. Moisture, which is readily absorbed by the epoxy matrix of composite laminates, also adversely affects the properties; this has the effect of plasticising the matrix and reducing T_g . A moisture content of 1% in a laminate can typically reduce T_g

from 175°C to 130°C. The combination of high temperatures and absorbed moisture can lead to significant strength reductions.

Two sets of tests were conducted at the tropical test facility; fatigue tests and static exposures tests. The specimens which were fatigue tested included one undamaged, one impact damaged and another manufactured with a teflon insert. Two teflon insert panels were used as the first was removed part way through the test period due to damage development. The environmental test fixture, shown in Fig. 4, used three "picture frame" shear fixtures, similar to the laboratory fixtures, connected in series. The train of "picture frame" rigs was connected to a hydraulic ram at one end and a load cell located at the other. As the frame was horizontal, a support structure, not shown in the figure, prevented the rigs sagging under their own weight. The fatigue tests were conducted at a peak load level of 38 kN (107 N/mm), cycling with a period of 40 seconds.

Fig. 4: Environmental test fixture arrangement.

Another three specimens were mounted in a stand, not under load, while being subjected to the same environmental conditions. The stand was positioned so that the specimens were exposed to maximum solar radiation. Following completion of the test period, all specimens were returned to the laboratory to assess the extent of any environmental degradation and damage growth. Residual strength tests will be conducted to determine whether long term cyclic loading combined with environmental exposure has a significant effect on the properties of the postbuckling panels.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Static Testing

Tests on undamaged panels showed that prior to buckling, the skin deflected out-of-plane due to both the unsymmetric lay-up of the skin and the initial imperfections. The panels buckled at approximately 31 kN (88 N/mm) (determined from strain reversal), developing a diagonal tension field typical of shear buckling. This was characterised by three half-waves in the two centre bays of the panel. As the load increased, the wave-length of the buckles decreased

slightly and small buckle peaks at the edges of the bays became more prominent. The out-of-plane displacements during testing were investigated qualitatively using the moiré interferometry technique. The peaks and troughs in the two central bays of the panel were not identical because of the different lay-up in the two bays. The out-of-plane displacements were also recorded using the LVDT with displacements of up to 3.2 mm measured. The buckled shape at a load of 70 kN (198 N/mm) is shown in Fig. 5. The presence of the 50 mm diameter teflon insert did not greatly influence the buckling load of the panels; however, the postbuckling shape was affected. It was observed that shortly after buckling, one of the buckle peaks was elongated and clearly extended into the delaminated region.

Fig. 5: Buckling shape of an undamaged panel at a load of 70 kN.

The experimental results showed that in the strain gauge locations, surface shear strains up to 22,000 $\mu\gamma$ were experienced before failure. Prior to buckling, the relationship between load and strain was approximately linear. Buckling was clearly identified by bifurcation of the back-to-back gauge strains. Following buckling, the strains increased at a higher rate due to the bending strains resulting from buckling.

The undamaged panels failed at loads of approximately 80 kN (226 N/mm) with fibre axial strains up to 10,000 $\mu\epsilon$ recorded. This was preceded by audible cracking from a load of 62 kN (175 N/mm). Ultimate failure of the undamaged panels was through fibre failure, fibre pull-out and delamination. It was characterised by extensive tension failure and fibre pull-out of the -45° fibres and appeared to initiate from the region where one buckle terminated at the centre stiffener. Failure spread rapidly horizontally across the panel, as shown in Fig. 6. Ultimate failure also resulted in extensive delamination along the vertical diagonal of the panels.

The process of failure in the panels with the teflon insert was very different. As previously mentioned, one of the buckle peaks extended into the delaminated region shortly after buckling. Cracking was heard at a load of 38 kN (107 N/mm) while significant delamination growth was noted at a load of 48 kN (136 N/mm). The resulting delaminated region can be

seen in Fig. 7. Following these events, the growth stabilised and load continued to be carried up to approximately 60 kN (170 N/mm) when significant fibre breakage occurred.

Fig. 6: Typical undamaged panel failure showing tension failure and fibre pull-out

Fig. 7: Teflon insert panel at 50 kN following delamination growth.

Laboratory Fatigue Testing

Fatigue tests have been conducted on several panels. One test was carried out at an R value of 0.4 with a minimum load of 20 kN (57 N/mm) and a peak load of 50 kN (141 N/mm). The peak load was equivalent to two thirds of the static ultimate load of the panel. This loading represents maximum fibre strains of approximately 6,000 $\mu\epsilon$ with out-of-plane displacements of up to 2.0 mm. The panel was cycled at this high strain level for three million cycles at 4 Hz with no resulting damage detected by ultrasonic C-scan. A test was carried out at an R value of -1.0 with a peak load of 50 kN (141 N/mm). This panel has been subjected to 60,000 cycles of fully reversed loading with no resulting damage.

Environmental Testing

The environmental test specimens underwent tropical exposure for up to 20.5 months, during which time the various specimens were subjected to a total of 370,000 cycles. A summary of the conditions experienced during this period are presented in Table 1. The relative humidity at the site was very high being above 90% for 60% of the time, dropping below 60% for only 6% of the time. The average daily maximum temperature was also quite high at 29.3°C. At the end of the test period, the moisture absorbed by the laminate had reached a level of approximately 0.7%, although it is expected that this level would fluctuate depending upon the temperature and humidity.

All specimens have exhibited signs of degradation due to exposure to UV radiation. This was characterised by the breaking down of the outer layer of the epoxy matrix which was then eroded by the wind and rain. In the static exposure specimens, the side that was facing the sun showed extensive signs of degradation. The outer layer of fibres were visible, many of which were loose. These fibres do appear to protect the underlying matrix, however under a

more erosive environment, it would be expected that the degradation could penetrate to a greater depth. This could seriously affect the integrity of the laminate in the long term and provides an indication of the importance of protecting composite structures from UV degradation. The fatigue panels were not subjected to the same levels of UV exposure, but some degradation was clearly evident.

Table 1: Summary of the environmental conditions at the tropical exposure site during the 20.5 month test period.

Average Daily Maximum Temperature	29.3°C
Average Daily Temperature	24.5°C
Average Daily Minimum Temperature	21.0°C
Average Daily Maximum Relative Humidity	99%
Average Daily Relative Humidity	88%
Average Daily Minimum Relative Humidity	65%
Proportion of Time Above 90% Relative Humidity	60%
Proportion of Time Below 60% Relative Humidity	6%
Total Rainfall	5,965 mm
Duration of Rainfall	757 hours
Total Solar Radiation	10,476 MJ/m ²

The undamaged fatigue specimen exhibited no signs of damage development as determined using C-scan following the test period. The impact damaged panel showed insignificant damage growth although the impact site was permanently “bubbled” following testing. The specimen with the 50 mm diameter artificial delamination underwent extensive delamination growth. This was clearly visible after 91,000 cycles when a C-scan was performed which showed delamination growth along the tension diagonal from the central delamination. The C-scan of this panel prior to testing is shown in Fig. 8(a) and after 91,000 cycles in Fig. 8(b). In Fig. 8(b), only the section along the tension diagonal was scanned at a lower resolution and damage was indicated by white regions; dark areas indicate damage in the other figures. The panel was then cycled for another 166,000 cycles before being removed. Another C-scan showed only a small amount of further delamination growth had occurred around the ends of the stiffeners, as shown in Fig. 8(c). A new delamination specimen was then placed in the test fixture for the remaining period. This panel underwent a total of 112,000 cycles and suffered very similar delamination growth to the previous panel after 257,000 cycles, as shown by the C-scan in Fig. 8(d). It should be pointed out that in Fig. 8(c), the damage above and to the left of the artificial delamination is not shown clearly.

From the various C-scans taken of the panels containing artificial delaminations, it appeared that the delamination reached a limit after approximately 100,000 cycles. The damage itself was similar in appearance to that experienced in the static testing of the same panels. However, the delamination growth occurred at a lower load level and became more widespread than in the static tests. In both the static and fatigue tests, the delamination growth was greater in the unsymmetric bay of the panel (the bay above the central stiffener in Fig. 8). After the delamination growth, the panels were still capable of carrying the cyclic load. These preliminary conclusions will be verified after further laboratory testing.

Fig. 8: C-scans of teflon insert panel (a) prior to testing, (b) after 91,000 cycles, (c) after 257,000 cycles and (d) replacement panel after 112,000 cycles.

CONCLUSIONS

The buckling and postbuckling performance of three-blade-stiffened carbon fibre/epoxy panels under shear has been investigated. Static and fatigue tests were conducted in a “picture frame” shear fixture. During static testing, buckling initiated at 31 kN (88 N/mm) and the panels exhibited significant postbuckling strength before failing at approximately 80 kN (226 N/mm). Ultimate failure of the panels was characterised by widespread delamination coupled with extensive fibre breakage of the -45° plies which were in tension. The presence of an introduced delamination affected the buckling mode shape and reduced the strength of the panels by 25%. These panels underwent delamination growth at 48 kN (136 N/mm) before failing at approximately 60 kN (170 N/mm).

The fatigue tests carried out so far have indicated that these panels are resistant to fatigue failures. Undamaged panels have been shown to be capable of sustaining cyclic loading up to two thirds of the static failure load without developing fatigue damage. Environmental testing proved the durability of undamaged and impact damaged panels, however panels containing a 50 mm diameter artificial delamination suffered delamination growth along the tension diagonal. These panels were still capable of carrying the cyclic load and the delamination appeared to stabilise after approximately 100,000 cycles. This testing program has demonstrated the inherent damage tolerance of the stiffened, postbuckling, composite panels.

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